

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

ORGANIZATIONAL AND PEDAGOGICAL ASPECTS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF SANOGENIC THINKING IN STUDENTS

Abdullayeva Muyassar Isakovna
Teacher of institut TMS in Tashkent

ОРГАНИЗАЦИОННО-ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИЕ АСПЕКТЫ РАЗВИТИЯ САНОГЕННОГО МЫШЛЕНИЯ У СТУДЕНТОВ

Абдуллаева Муяссар Исаковна
Преподаватель института ТМС в Ташкенте

Abstract

The article covers organizational, legal, pedagogical and psychological aspects of the development of sanogenic thinking of students. Pedagogical and psychological possibilities for the development of sanogenic thinking of students are explored by proposing ways to achieve a high level of spiritual, mental and physical health.

Аннотация

В статье освещено об организационных, правовых, педагогических и психологических аспектах развития саногенного мышления студентов. Педагогические и психологические возможности развития саногенного мышления студентов исследуются путем предложения путей достижения высокого уровня духовного, психического и физического здоровья.

Keywords: Sanogenic thinking, psychological and pedagogical aspect, student, healthcare.

Ключевые слова: Саногенное мышление, психолого-педагогический, аспект, студент, здравоохранение.

An important factor in the social stability that has developed in the world is the preservation of the spiritual, physical and mental health of young people, who are the heirs of our national culture, the formation of a healthy, socially stable, adapted to living conditions and happy personality. In this regard, the most appropriate approach to ensuring human health in the education system is the health approach, which describes the characteristics of the impact of education on the health of participants in the educational process and health. Activity through the organization of a (sanogenic) educational environment acquires current importance.

In recent years, there has been an increase in the quality and efficiency of the education system in our country, the formation of modern knowledge and skills among students and young people, close cooperation and integration of the education system and the field of science and education. ensure integrity and continuity. In particular, since one of the priority tasks of the education system of our republic is a responsible attitude towards one's health and the health of others in the educational process as a high social value, all aspects of students' activities are aimed at achieving a high level of spiritual development, , mental, physical health.

Article 46, paragraph 4, of the Law "On Education" states that "taking into account the psychological and unique characteristics, physical and mental health, physiological development of students, physical, mental, sensory (sense) or focusing on creating conditions for the education of persons with mental deviations" [1]. From this point of view, when

preparing future teachers for professional activities, it is necessary to realize their health potential, develop sanogenic thinking, and provide methodological recommendations for avoiding various factors that are harmful to their health during the educational process. In future teaching activities, it is necessary to create a sanogenic environment to promote a healthy lifestyle..

Article 47, paragraph 5 of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 28, 2022 "On the Development Strategy of the new Uzbekistan for 2022-2026": have the necessary conditions taking into account physiological development" [2]. To do this, universities must pay attention to the mental and emotional characteristics of students in the educational process, increase the efficiency of professional and methodological work that is important for their physiological development, and organize effective training against professional, psychological and physiological stress in the process of teaching practice..

As stated in the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 29, 2019 No. PF-5712 "On approval of the Concept for the development of the public education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030," physically healthy and energetic education of the child with the aim of "popularizing the principles of healthy nutrition for schoolchildren" [3], with teaching the science "Children's Anatomy and Physiology", the characteristics of the child's body, the characteristics of the physiological processes occurring in them are healthy and it is necessary to give scientific and methodological recommendations for mastering the

principles of healthy nutrition and assess the competence of the practical application of these recommendations on the basis of independent tasks and in the process of teaching practice.

Global changes taking place in the education system of all developed countries of the world create a need for intellectually capable, healthy, creatively thinking specialists.

Before moving on to the description of sanogenic thinking, it is necessary to emphasize points aimed at preventing possible misunderstandings in the understanding of this term. In psychology, thinking is the mental process of modeling the patterns of the surrounding world based on axiomatic rules [1]. However, in psychology there are many other definitions.

For example: the highest stage of human data processing, the process of establishing connections between objects or events in the surrounding world; or - the process of reflecting important properties of objects, as well as connections between them, which lead to the emergence of ideas about objective reality. Debate over the definition continues to this day.

Thinking is the highest level of human knowledge; the process of cognition of the surrounding real world, the basis of which is education and constant replenishment of the stock of concepts and ideas; involves making new judgments (implementing conclusions).

In pathopsychology and neuropsychology, thinking is one of the highest mental functions. It is considered as an activity that has motivation, goals, actions and a system of operations, results and management.

In psychology, thinking is usually called a set of mental actions with the help of which a certain problem or task is solved in the mind. Thinking under the influence of need is activated from the moment when the goal is defined and in a certain situation an obstacle to achieving it appears: there are not enough means, knowledge or abilities to achieve the goal and satisfy the need. This thinking is the work of images, signs, symbols in the mind to make the right decision. When solving "from point A to point B" or any other task, thinking must develop a course of action that will lead to the desired result. In this case, the purpose of this thinking is determined by our need, situation and task.

But when we solve internal problems (for example, how to relieve pain and suffering from resentment, or jealousy, or experienced failure), then this is also thinking, but it changes its character, since it pursues not external, but internal goals, for example, achieving a more complete integration of our self-image and our actual behavior; and in some cases it is aimed at increasing joy and satisfaction in existence or achieving meaning in life. Unfortunately, this thinking has not been sufficiently studied in psychology. Those protective mechanisms with which the reader became acquainted earlier act as "involuntary thinking", the purpose of which is to reduce suffering. In sanogenic thinking, this process occurs consciously, voluntarily; the purpose of such thinking is also consciously determined. For example, I can think about a situation

so I don't get upset with others or get jealous of a friend. But the fact is that no one taught us this idea. Therefore, it is very important for the student to become familiar with how sanogenic thinking works..

But to better understand this, let's review our ideas about pathogenic thinking so that the differences can be more easily identified.

A figurative representation of situations in which certain life events occurred allows you to "play" them in your head. Anyone who often "replays" in his head the situation of failure, which he, for example, experienced in a past exam, unwittingly re-experiences the stress. Such negative reinforcement of one's own thoughts is a manifestation of pathogenic thinking that gives rise to illness and neurosis. Pathogenic thinking multiplies a person's suffering: after all, with the help of his thinking, he reproduces the situation of stress countless times, putting himself into a state of chronic stress that destroys the body [4].

Sanogenic thinking extinguishes the "negative charge" contained in memories of situations in which a person experienced suffering. It frees the images from this charge and thereby relieves the tension caused by it.

This occurs through the use of the extinction effect, when situations that were very unpleasant in the past are "played out" in the imagination in a state of rest and detachment. As a result, tolerance for previously traumatic situations increases and sensitivity to them decreases.

This does not mean that a person will become like a tree and ordinary stimuli will not act on him. But his peculiarity is that in a situation where he is offended, he will experience the offense, but then he will eliminate this offense much faster than someone who does not have this mindset.

The following features are characteristic of sanogenic thinking.

Firstly, the dynamism of the connection between our Self and the world of images that reflect life situations. On the one hand, the ability of the I to completely merge with them and charge them with energy and activity, when effective activity is required, complete immersion in activity, in communication, in creativity, as a result of which everything except the subject of activity disappears. This focus and absorption leads to increased efficiency and eliminates side emotions that interfere with performance. On the other hand, our Self is characterized by separation from situations and images saturated with negative emotional content. This feature of thinking manifests itself in reflection or introspection, in which our I makes the images themselves and emotional reactions to them the object of consideration.

The subject separates himself from his own experiences and observes them. This separation of the Self from feelings helps to weaken experiences and frees images from their "emotional energy." In fact, try to imagine from the outside how joy flows through you, and you will feel that joy has weakened or disappeared completely. Of course, when it comes to joy, we are sad

that it has disappeared. But the fact that the experience has disappeared is important.

Not only positive, but also negative experiences disappear if we make them the object of mental observation from the outside.

If I manage to consider myself as being offended, to imagine the internal structure of the offense that arose in a specific situation, then gradually the experience of offense disappears. This observation from the outside and replaying the situation of resentment can also be done in writing, which is often used by psychotherapists.

Secondly, with sanogenic thinking, introspection, or reflection directed inward, is carried out against the background of deep inner peace, as a result of which the subject reproduces, "plays out" situations of stress experienced previously, against the background of relaxation (relaxation). This kind of thinking creates a fading effect. Images saturated with affect, as we showed earlier, are gradually freed from emotional content, and their reproduction in consciousness does not cause a stress reaction[4].

When we reproduce a stressful situation against a background of peace, adaptation to such situations occurs, so that when they are repeated, sharp and strong feelings no longer arise.

Thirdly, sanogenic thinking is based on a specific representation in consciousness of the structure of those mental states that are controlled. Thus, thinking about an offense involves knowing how an offense works, what its structure is. This kind of introspection is impossible without knowledge of the basics of the psychology of feelings and personality psychology. To think about how my resentment, my vanity, my shame and my fear work, you must first of all know how these psychological realities generally work. Therefore, we have described in detail the structure of the basic emotions: resentment, guilt, shame, envy, vanity and pride, fear. If you re-read these chapters, you will get material for introspection. Self-observation involves knowledge of the psychological mechanisms of the objects of reflection. Anyone who knows how his offense works can make it an object of introspection and sanogenic thinking. Anyone who does not know this will fail, since he will reproduce in his imagination only images that cause the experience of resentment. Therefore, the study of introspection methods should take place under the supervision of a psychologist-teacher, who helps eliminate gross mistakes that the student initially makes. Only by mastering the basics of sanogenic thinking and acquiring the appropriate mental skills can a person independently continue to work on self-improvement and improvement of his psyche.

Fourthly, mastering sanogenic thinking involves broadening one's horizons and internal culture, which primarily consists of understanding the origins of stereotypes, programs of cultural behavior, cultural history, especially the structure of the archetype. When we think "he acted unfairly," what does that mean? What is justice? Where does our sense of justice come from? This kind of understanding allows us to correctly comprehend the offense that arises from the unfair act

of another. Why did he do this? To answer this question, it is not enough to have an idea of what is fair or unfair. You also need to know what defines behavior in a broad sense in order to understand the specific behavior of another who offends you. If we think about vice or duty, we must understand the true content of these concepts, their internal structure.

Fifthly, sanogenic thinking is impossible without a sufficiently developed level of concentration and concentration on the objects of thought.

The process of introspection is impossible if our attention "floats", is scattered and cannot focus on the mental objects of introspection. Therefore, the formation of sanogenic thinking is a prerequisite for concentration of attention.

The pedagogical process is, first of all, a process of joint activity of two individuals, each of which represents a dialectical unity of the body and mental properties. Therefore, the main thing to begin the process of educating and training a future teacher is to develop the ability to take care of the health of children, in which sanogenic thinking, which represents the interdependence of teachers and students, provides an invaluable service.]. Sanogenic thinking is one of the most reliable methods of healing the soul and body, through mental support of crisis situations that have arisen in a person's life [Orlov Yu.M. Health-improving] leads to the formation of a broad worldview and thinking, new innovative ideas and humanitarian characteristics [].

Sanogenic thinking ("sanos" (lat.) - to heal, heal, console, encourage, put in order and "geno" (lat.) - to heal) is to create a way of thinking that heals, consoles and inspires [Ismailov, reflex, page 47].

Translated from Greek, sanogen means bringing health (sanos - improving health; genos - carrier). In the process of developing sanogenic thinking, students rethink their worldview and opinions, which is carried out in accordance with the improvement and growth of their personal relationships and activities [Kucharova, p.61]. By accepting oneself and accepting other students, sanogenic reflection provides a person with self-confidence, harmony in relationships with other people, and strengthens confidence in the world. The main method for the development of sanogenic thinking is autopsychanalysis of feelings, which is carried out during training aimed at self-awareness and cognition.

In our opinion, sanogenic thinking is designed to activate the internal potential resources of students' personality within the limits of health (voluntary, creative, emotional, social, physical) and ensure the development of positive socio-psychological relationships in various spheres of life and activity. activity; consists in choosing optimal behavior programs.

In any society, in any socio-economic and political situation, the health of young people is an urgent problem that determines the future of the country, the gene pool of the nation, scientific and economic potential. Society, among other demographic indicators, is a sensitive barometer of the country's

socio-economic development[4]. The concept of sanogenic thinking in pedagogical analysis is based on the thesis about the priority of cognitive assessment in relation to pedagogical tasks and emotional experiences arising in connection with the educational process, which is the student's use of his thoughts to influence emotions. and is a process of acquiring skills associated with constructive methods of solving problems of pedagogical activity by changing cognitive assessments [5]. The role of biology in developing such potential of future teachers is incomparable.

Pedagogy is directly and indirectly related to physiology, and physiology is the natural scientific basis of pedagogy and psychology. Human anatomy and physiology are studied as the most comprehensive science among the biological sciences. It is impossible to study the activities of the body without having information about the structure and functions of the body's organs. Especially in pedagogy, pediatric anatomy and physiology, the development of the higher nervous system, the uniqueness of the nervous system, the first and second signaling systems, as well as information about the activity and development of the sense organs, the main motor apparatus, the heart, blood vessels and the respiratory system are described. relies on data. Knowledge of the physiological foundations of psychological phenomena creates the opportunity for pedagogy to clearly and accurately assimilate and understand some factors of upbringing and teaching, and helps to successfully solve many problems of increasing the efficiency of the educational process.

Heredity, environment and education play an important role in human development. Hereditary characteristics are among the objective factors in the formation of personality. The anatomical structure, physiological movements, type of nerves, basic unconditioned reflexes in the human body are inherited from parents. In modern pedagogy and psychology, the role of biological factors in the development of human personality and behavior is important. Some biogenetic scientists (E. Thorndike) put forward the idea that a human child will have all the signs of a future person even when the mother is young, and some of them believe that consciousness and mental abilities are passed on from generation to generation. Some scientists also associate a person's moral growth with heredity. Consequently, heredity is the anatomical, physiological, psychological aspects that determine the uniqueness of a person, which are transmitted by parents through genetic changes. Of course, one cannot deny the uniqueness of the biological factor in human

formation, but human characteristics - mental and physical abilities for work, thinking and speech can also be inherited, but for the development of these innate abilities, a human child must live among people, have relationships in society must be installed [6] .

I.M. Spivak talks about sanogenic features of behavior. In his opinion, sanogenic behavior supports health and well-being as an active way to ensure human development [7, p.470]. Behavior is controlled by thinking and can be divided into two groups: pathogenic and sanogenic. Thus, a person's behavior can have different positive or negative effects on his well-being, mood, health and other aspects of his life. Situational behavior has a positive effect on health and well-being and is sanogenic. On the contrary, behavior that is inappropriate to the situation has a negative impact on a person's life; this behavior is called pathogenic. Pathogenic and sanogenic consequences of individual behavior are associated with unhealthy and healthy lifestyles, respectively.

References

1. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education". - Tashkent, 09/23/2020. www.lex.uz.
2. Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 28, 2022 "On the development strategy of the new Uzbekistan for 2022-2026" No. PF No. 60. <https://lex.uz/docs/5841063>.
3. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 29, 2019 No. PF-5712 "On approval of the concept of development of the public education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" // <https://lex.uz/documents/-4312785/>
4. Orlov Yu.M. Main features of sanogenic thinking // <https://psy.wikireading.ru/9457/>.
5. Ismailov M.Q. Components of development of sanogenic thinking in students and its pedagogical-psychological features // *Oriental Renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*. September 2021. VOLUME 1 | ISSUE 8 ISSN 2181-1784 Scientific Journal Impact Factor SJIF 2021: 5.423. - B. 509-522.
6. Abdullaeva Sh.A., Askarov A.D. General pedagogy. Textbook for bachelors of non-teaching universities. Tashkent-2019. - 359 p.
7. Spivak I.M. The essence and structure of sanogenic behavior from the perspective of the ontological approach to learning // *International Journal of Developmental and Educational Psychology INFAD Revista de Psicología*, N°1-Vol.2, 2013. ISSN: 0214-9877. pp:469-482.